

Health Studies Australian National Data Asset (HeSANDA)

Reusing data to accelerate research and better health outcomes

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HeSANDA is a national initiative of the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) and is supported by National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS). It is a collaboration of 9 HeSANDA nodes that represent over 70 health research organisations across Australia.

HeSANDA began in 2021 and continues under the ARDC's People Research Data Commons.

Learn more about HeSANDA
bit.ly/hesanda ►

Visit Health Data Australia
bit.ly/health-data-australia ►

Get to know the People Research Data Commons
bit.ly/people-rdc ►

The Health Studies Australian National Data Asset (HeSANDA) is a national program that makes health and medical research data easier to find. It facilitates access, sharing and reuse of research data, resulting in a reduction in research waste, improvements in researcher collaboration, and an opportunity to answer new research questions. It aims to support more efficient and effective research to help improve health outcomes.

The research community across Australia has been working together through HeSANDA to develop **Health Data Australia**, a catalogue for health and medical researchers to register a description of their research so it's easy to discover. A federated structure of partners across Australia then links researchers and facilitates data sharing and data access. This is possible through the searchable online catalogue and a secure access request portal.

Importantly, the researchers who created the data always maintain control over their data and determine with whom it is shared.

In Phase 1, HeSANDA focussed on investigator-initiated and academic clinical trials. As part of the People Research Data Commons, phase 2 (2023-2028) will provide opportunities to consolidate capability for clinical trials, extend the approach to other health study types, and deploy new capabilities such as secure access environments.

The Value of HeSANDA and Health Data Australia

For Australia

Increases Australia's return on investment in health and medical research by enabling researchers to reuse existing data to inform new research questions and initiate new research collaborations. This will accelerate research answers and extend the value of consumer/participant contributions in a systematic and meaningful way.

For Research Participants and the Community

- Allows participants to contribute to more research without requiring more of their time or effort
- Makes the most out of the data that participants provide
- Participants may view this as a meaningful contribution to more than one research project.

For Research Organisations

- Raises the profile, status, research reputation and ranking of institutions and the researchers through increased citations, collaborations, and grant applications
- Creates more opportunity for impactful projects
- Enhances research rigour, i.e. by making research easier to reproduce
- Increases productivity through the increase in the number of research outputs
- Could lead to a positive impact on the number of students, commercialisation and quality and value of research grants.

For Health Services

- Supports improved research practices in health services
- Raises the profile, status and researcher reputation through increased citations, collaborations, and grant applications
- Increases the use of research data that has been created and supported through health service funding.

For Researchers Who Created the Data (*Data providers*)

Provides a systematic approach for researchers across Australia to:

- Gain increased recognition and visibility for their research
- Extend the life of their research
- Meet their responsibilities to share data from publicly funded research projects
- Facilitate new collaborations to expand their research impact.

It is anticipated that this will lead to:

- Increased ability to understand and answer specific questions and generate new hypotheses
- More publications and citations, new students, successful grants and a sense of helping others across the country
- Better access to guidance, standards and governance around data sharing.

For Researchers Seeking Data (*Data users*)

- Inspires new research questions and provides opportunities to build richer and more extensive datasets
- Provides a systematic and clear mechanism to create new collaborations
- Reduces research costs and duplication and saves time by hosting a catalogue of available research in one place and a clear pathway to request data
- Accelerates research discovery.

To the Funder

- Increases the return on investment through the reuse of research data
- Could lead to a positive impact on the value of the research grant and enhanced awareness of the funding body.

How it Works

The HeSANDA Network

There are 9 HeSANDA nodes that represent 72 health research organisations across Australia.

Melbourne Academic Centre for Health (MACH)

Clinical Trials Consortium Node

Administered by: The University of Melbourne

Mental Health Node

Administered by: Deakin University

Monash and Partners Node

Administered by: Monash University

National Cancer Cooperative Trials Groups Node

Administered by: Australasian Leukaemia and Lymphoma Group (ALLG)

Northern Australia Node

Administered by: Menzies School of Health Research

Queensland Node

Administered by: Health Translation Queensland in collaboration with CSIRO's Australian e-Health Research Centre and Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF).

South Australia Node

Administered by: South Australian Health and Medical Research Institute (SAHMRI)

Sydney Health Partners Node

Administered by: NHMRC Clinical Trials Centre at The University of Sydney

Western Australia Node

Administered by: Curtin University

Australian Research Data Commons

The ARDC is enabled by NCRIS

At the ARDC, we drive development of world-class national digital research infrastructure that gives Australian researchers competitive advantage through data and supports research impact.

The ARDC is Australia's leading facility for research data infrastructure. We facilitate access to research data sets and tools from academia, industry and government for all Australian researchers.

We run programs and form partnerships that ensure Australian researchers are internationally competitive through having access to high-quality data assets, platforms, infrastructure, policies, people and training to transform our lives.

Solving society's greatest challenges takes the collective efforts of society. Through our collaborations and partnerships — national and international — we are ensuring that valuable data and software assets are developed, made accessible and sustained for everyone.

The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

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